
*Photobioreactor for WP1 and WP2
installed
at CSIC location and functional
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**Photobioreactor for WP1 and WP2 installed at CSIC
location and functional**

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1. Design of a photobioreactor for directed evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli*.

The small scale bioreactor system was designed following the necessities of CSIC partner and PhotoSynH2 project consortium for the direct evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli* at small scale, using improved technique for a two stages cells and phages growth and evolution. The design of the bioreactors was done after an analysis of the existing systems and scientific reactors for using on *E. coli* and designing improvements needed for PhotoSynH2 direct evolution.

The single 40 ml reactor was designed using a 3D design software and simulations.

Figure 1. 3D Design of the 40 ml photobioreactor

2. From design to 3D printers for the custom made photobioreactors

After the 3D design the small scale photobioreactors have been realized using 3D printers to construct the customized improved systems.

Figure 2. The 3D printer and one of the 16 PBR realized including 3D designed and printed pieces of Bioreactors and equipped with electronics.

3. Design of array of 16 photobioreactors for directed evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli*.

The concept of the system for directed evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli* was customized as an array of 16 photobioreactors in two stages connected with micropumps for dosing nutrients, chemicals, cells, phages, excess of culture and level control. The array has been designed as inserted in a compact three floors system in order to be moved, if necessary, in an easy manner and to be easy to operate. The photobioreactors system arrays has been designed using the 3D design software for succeed structure custom realization.

Figure 3. The 3D design of the array system of 16 PBR connected with 32 micropumps for dosing nutrients and manage the two stage cells-phages PhotoSynH2 direct cells evolution

4. Construction of array of 16 photobioreactor for directed evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli*

The array of the system for directed evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli* was realized and tested in all its functionalities.

Figure 4. Details of the first floor with 16 PBR

Figure 5. Photobioreactors system custom realized for cells direct evolution

Figure 6. The back of the compact system realized. PBRs Electronics and pumps are evident.

5. Summary of the characteristics of the system realized

The design Photobioreactor and PBR array system for direct evolution of *Synechocystis* and *E. coli* was designed and customized with improvements to use two stages cells and phages for direct evolution. The PBRs array system was customized and made by M2M and the principal features are: System with Nr.16 x 40ml Bioreactor; 2-Phases system 8-PBRs Cells + 8 PBRs Cells+Phages; Nr.32 micro-pumps controlled connected to PBRs ; 3D designed and 3D-printed customized improvements; Led IR for OD measurements and control; Led for Lighting; Stirring system with magnetic bar with variable speed; Heating System with aluminum cylinders and heaters controlled, and cooling profile air forces improved

6. Photosynh2 Phagestat system characteristics

Phage-Assisted Continuous Evolution requires the use of complex bioreactors with specific features (overview in Figure 7), and specific requirements and improvements based on experiments in close collaboration with CSIC, the main features and requirements are explained below.

- Versatility; as illustrated in Figure 8 (A and B), connections between the different culture vessels may differ between experiments. Depending on the evolutionary trajectories and adaptation conditions designed for the evolution of a certain molecule/genetic part, the flow between the vessels needs to be readjust. We need a system that allows for this modularity while keeping robustness.

This versatility materializes in different parts of the design:

- Specific lid: the number of input and output ports is experiment-specific, as well as the length of the output tube, which depends on the desired volume of the culture vessel.

- Specific lid: the caps of vials, with different numbers, lengths, shapes, connections of tubes inlet and outlet are different and experiment-specific and need customization based on experiment
- Extra pumps: commercially available bioreactors often have two pumps per culture vessel. However, for our purpose, not only media gets in and waste gets out, as sometimes, inducers need to be pumped in and extra output ports for serial sampling is required. Therefore, more pumps need to be added.
- Fluorescent feedback. Fluorescent measurements are not a main feature added in regular bioreactors. Not only we required that but also a feedback control based on fluorescent similarly to the one based on OD (known as turbidostat).
- Parallel evolutions in multiple small-scale bioreactors.
- Air inlet/outlet: in order to maintain equal pressure values inside and outside of the bioreactors while still keeping sterility, we need an extra hole with a specific 0,22 μM filter.
- Robust and consistent measurements.
- Direct assistance and contact with manufacturers and continuous updates. Along the research, new implementations or software updates may need to be done, this is only achievable when the manufacturer and the user are in continuous contact and in understanding of both parts needs.

Figure 7. Standard set-up required for Phage-Assisted Continuous Evolution. Turbidostat is where the host cells are grown and Phagestat is where evolution happen.

Figure 8. Experimental design of the evolution of a molecule/genetic part in three different hosts (A) in parallel (B) in a serial set up.

Figure 9: Different experiments done with phagestat system cultures made in close collaboration with CSIC.

Figure 10: data from different experiments done with culture system

Commercial available bioreactors analyzed: after intense research of the commercially available bioreactors, we found four (Figure 10) that offer a few of the features needed:

- eVOLVER; reference Wong, B., Mancuso, C., Kiriakov, S. et al. Precise, automated control of conditions for high-throughput growth of yeast and bacteria with eVOLVER. *Nat Biotechnol* 36, 614–623 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4151>

- Chi.bio; reference H. Steel, R. Habgood, C. Kelly, A Papachristodoulou, Chi.Bio: An open-source automated experimental platform for biological science research, BioRxiv, 2019, DOI: 10.1101/796516
- Ogibio; reference <https://ogibio.co.uk/product/ogibioreactor/>
- Multicultivator; reference <https://photo-bio-reactors.com/products/multi-cultivators/>

They, however, would need several adjustments and customizations, experiment specific, with different functions needed for PhotosynH2 Phagestat. For illustration we are naming at least one important feature that is missing in the commercially available bioreactor and is necessary in our case. All systems are extremely good systems, and was important for inspiration and improve features for PhosynH2 phagestat. Evolver; good system, the commercially available one only allows for one input and one output. No connection between the vessels is possible. Chi.bio; good system, offers the most features but needs other customizations for phagestat, for the feedback control in all the needed cases. Ogibio; good system, offer several features, in project several key features mode in all the vessels needs for phagestat, and several other pumps needs per different vessels. Multicultivator; good system, needs some other features for modularity interchangeable pumps, as it offers a close circuit of inflow from the same media and output.